

OPTIMIZATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES
OF PLATANUS ORIENTALIS LNafees Farooq¹, Dr. Ayoub Rashid^{*2}^{1,2}Department of Chemistry, Government College University, Lahore, Pakistan¹nafeesfarooq123@gmail.com, ²ayoubrashid_gcu75@yahoo.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18618100>**Keywords**Antidiabetic, methanol, solutions,
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Abstract

Platanus Orientalis L. used to treat different diseases in ancient times. Purpose of study to find its chemical activities in different agents or solvents. Two types of solvents used, ethanol and methanol. Different biological activities performed like antioxidant, antibacterial and antidiabetic. Characterization of plant GC-MS and HPLC performed. Liquid nitrogen quenching is performed, then made composition with ethanol and methanol. This composition was further used to perform activities. Before this yield percentage had been calculated. In antioxidant TPC, TFC, DPPH, ABTS and metal chelating was performed and graph also drawn. In antibacterial two types of enzymes used which is *E. coli* and other is *Bacillus subtilis*, here peniciline was standard. To perform antibacterial Disc Diffusion method used. In antidiabetic in vitro activity performed. This plant has a variety of medicinal uses. It mostly found in Greece, Italy, Iran and also in US.

INTRODUCTION

Platanus orientalis also called plane tree. This plant is very popular due to its beauty and shadow. During Roman and Greek time, it is also considered as fortune plant. Plane tree act as essential element of environment which help to protect and clean atmosphere from pollutants.(Ciaffi et al., 2022) Only in Italy it is supposed to be an endangered species due to some environmental factor but not in other countries. Study of *platanus orientalis* could be very help helpful due to its interdisciplinary approach means that all possible branches of science botany, environmental etc. To protect plant diversity there is need to find scientific solutions.(Rosati et al., 2015) plants species benefits for social and economic life. They can reduce air and noise pollution, help in ecosystem, could provide habitat and also help to maintain our climate.(Sevik et al., 2019) Its common name is chinara and can used as pain reliever and also used

to cure inflammation. In past *platanus orientalis* used a treating agent or medicine. It is mostly used to clean climate. To cure tooth pain it was used by old hakims and Persian scientist. (Hajhashemi et al., 2011) 118 species of plane trees are widely distributed in Italy. The most famous is *platanus orientalis*. For the protection of ancient trees in Italy one Law is passed. These trees are present in urban areas in a good quantity need to care first.(Ciaffi et al., 2018) leaves of this plants are very beautiful containing lobes, are very wide, small flower and thick bark, height 170 feet, and diameter of trunk is very high and that plant is of course *platanus orientalis*.(BERRY, 1914) due to its large medicinal effects it was also used to treat some kind of allergy (allergic rhinitis).In past, For the absorption of metals that are toxic for human health absorbed by tree bark because tree bark can act as bio monitors. Bark can detect the amount of metal in environment.(Isinkaralar, 2022) All

plant part lies on exfoliating scale. These plants show vegetative reproduction. Disease of plant is canker stain. US first reported this pathogen. Disease result is destruction of xylem and phloem which leads to plant death.(Derviş et al., 2020).

Plant Metabolites

Some diseases only treated by plant components. Obesity is the major problem in all countries. All medicines fail to cure this disease. Only natural products like plant can treat this, plants can act as antiobesity agent. Obesity can cause different diseases. There is an enlargement in cell size or increase in cells. (Gooda Sahib et al., 2012) Metabolites are of two types.

Primary metabolites type of metabolites that present in living organism e.g. plant which are essential for normal growth of plant. They are the key for the survival of an organism. Major process that occurs in plant like photosynthesis can proceed. The other process like respiration can proceed normally in an organism without any other metabolites. Examples are amino acids, carbohydrates etc. Other type of metabolites are secondary metabolites which are not essential for normal growth of plant or any other living organism. Organism can survive without these metabolites but their long-term absence in organism can affect working or growth. Antioxidant agents, smell, taste etc.(Raghuveer et al., 2015). Drugs we used daily as medicines are the secondary metabolites. Plant leaves, roots, stem are used to extract secondary metabolites by plant cell and tissue culture technologies which are very beneficial. In pharmaceutical secondary metabolites are the main brick of this building, they are the key source for file span on earth. Secondary metabolites adopt every environment very easily. A large variety of organic compounds produced by plants are called secondary metabolites. In some cases desired products cannot be obtained from plant cell culture techniques, so need to promote and find solution for more production of metabolites.(Hussain et al., 2012). O₃ is a pollutant which causes a stress in plants. This stress can stop the enzyme activity. Production of secondary metabolites will be more. Carbon flows toward metabolic pathways and

produce secondary metabolites.(Singh et al., 2023) secondary metabolites actually derived from primary metabolites. Among all living organism, plant produce more secondary metabolites. In 1970s it was considered that secondary metabolites are only the waste products so there was no use of these at that time. (Jacoby et al., 2021).

Platanus Orientalis

Platanus leaves contain pollen that may also found in fossil. (Tschan, Denk, & von Balthazar, 2008) LM and SEM techniques are used to measure plant morphology. (Carpenter, Hill, & Jordan, 2005) in platanus species sow unique characteristics in their leaves, fruit etc. (Manchester, 1986). Platanaceae belong to different platanus species and each leaf have same epidermal structure.(Zlatko Kvaček, Manchester, & Guo, 2001)pistillate and staminate flower both are same in some ways but stamens are absent in them.(Mindell, Stockey, & Beard, 2006)crude extract of platanus orientalis were used to protect from diarrhea.(Bashir, Khan, Ahmad, & Shah, 2023) some region have a large amount of plane tree means have large amount of pollen during march April. This pollen may be benefit but during this month it can cause allergy. (Lara Espinar, 2023). Gratani et al. 2020, worked on *P. acerifolia* trees (in various areas of Rome) having similar size (Gratani, Vasheka, & Bigaran, 2020). Saraçoğlu & Bükler studied *Platanus anatolius* as well as *Platanus orientalis* and compare their effectivity in treating osteoarthritis, gout besides investigating their antidepressant effects (SARAÇOĞLU & BIYIK, 2021). Wu et al. 2022 reported that there is demand of antibacterial medications, probably for treating *S. aureus* (Wu et al., 2022). Wang et al. 2017 worked on exopolysaccharide which have ability to be used as natural source for additives. It was found in *Lactobacillus plantarum* KX041 culture (Wang et al., 2017). Păltinean et al. studied medicinal uses of *Fumaria schleicheri* Soy. Will. (commonly found in East as well as South Europe) for treating hepatobiliary as well as digestive diseases. (Păltinean et al., 2022).

Material and Method

This include the information about chemicals, apparatus, reagents, techniques and instruments that have been used during the experimental work. For antibacterial and antioxidant activity, sample

preparation with different solvent composition, extraction process, and solvent composition from extract all have been explained in this section.

Table: List of apparatus and tableware are given below:

Tableware	Apparatus
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Beakers ● Test Tubes ● Funnel ● Separating Funnel ● Condenser ● Petri dishrs ● Glass vials ● Round bottom flask ● Measuring sylinder ● Pipette ● Centrifuge Tubes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water Bath ● Motor ● Thermometer ● Aluminium foil ● Stirrer ● Scale ● Tweezer ● Marker ● Spatula ● Micropipette

Chemicals and Solvent:

Below is a list of every chemical and solvent that was employed during the research. Different instruments are depicted in the figure below.

Rotary Evaporator

Sonicator

Hotplate

ABTS and DPPH tests were performed to access the extracts in antioxidant activity using a Spectrophotometer. After introducing a blank solvent into the instrument, the standard solution absorption and different solution composition were observed.

Collection of plant “*platanus orientalis L*”.

The first step is to collect the sample relevant to research question and that is *platanus orientalis L*. Botanical Garden of GCU have a diverse array of plant species, each plant in garden has its own characteristics. While collecting leaves ethical

practices should be follow to insure the minimum effects on ecosystem and environment. Collection can be used for identification, species documentation and preservation as a specimen. *Platanus orientalis L*. common name used maple leaves were acquired from botanical garden of Government College University Lahore.

Preparation of Sample

Different type of sample is prepared during this work. First one sample is prepared for biological activities which are antioxidant and antibacterial and second one is for characterization.

Preparation of Extract for Antioxidant and Antibacterial:

The Following were the primary steps taken during this sampling.

Liquid Nitrogen Quenching

After cleaning the leaves with tissue paper that plucked from botanical garden. After washing, plucked leaves were instantly quenched with

liquid nitrogen and ground to a fine powder using a pestle mortar. While crushing these leaves add liquid nitrogen with time. Use nitrogen until leaves changed into fine powder.

Creation of Solvent Composition:

Water and ethanol were combined in various ratios to create six unique solvent compositions, each of which had a 100ml volume.

Table: Plant Extract Compositions.

No. of compositions	Composition based on ethanol %age	Percentage of ethanol	Percentage of Water
1	100	100	0
2	80	80	20
3	60	60	40
4	40	40	60
5	20	20	80
6	0	0	100

Water and Methanol were combined in various ratios to create six unique solvent compositions, each of which had a 100ml volume.

No. of compositions	Composition based on Methanol %age	Percentage of Methanol	Percentage of Water
1	100	100	0
2	80	80	20
3	60	60	40
4	40	40	60
5	20	20	80
6	0	0	100

Sample Addition:

On an electronic scale, 2gm of powder sample was weighed and added to each mixture. These samples left in dark for 48 hours. These compositions were placed in centrifuge tubes.

Filtration:

After putting the sample in orbital shaker, next process is to filtrate our sample, before filtration each sample need to be shaken. Whatman No. 1 filter paper is used for filtration.

Sonication and Shaking:

Each sample were subjected to sonication process for about 30-35 min at lowest temperature and that temperature should be below 10 Celsius. After sonication samples were then put through in orbital shaker for three hours.

Rotary Evaporator:

Rotary evaporator is an equipment that used to evaporate excess solvent using heat energy. Temperature scale is used; high temperature provide heat which help in evaporation. In solvent after evaporation pure solvent is left behind. This method helps us to get desired substance. It is efficient because it provides more surface area to

solvent, more evaporation process occurs. In results, components are separated from complex mixtures.

Calculation of Extract Yield (%).

The following equation was used to compute the extract yield.

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{mass of extract}}{\text{mass of leaves material taken (gm)}} \times 100$$

1mg of the extracted samples was added to each solvent associate with sample extract composition to develop sample solutions. By combining solvent solution (ethanol, methanol) with water, as a result various compositions of sample extract can be created.

Preparation of sample for Antioxidant Activity:

For ethanol

Time period for sonication will be 15mins.

No. Of compositions	Composition percentage with reference to ethanol	Percentage of ethanol	Percentage of Water
1	100	100	0
2	80	80	20
3	60	60	40
4	40	40	60
5	20	20	80
6	0	0	100

For Methanol:

Time period for sonication will be 15mins.

No. Of compositions	Composition percentage with reference to Methanol	Percentage of Methanol	Percentage of Water
1	100	100	0
2	80	80	20
3	60	60	40
4	40	40	60
5	20	20	80
6	0	0	100

Antioxidant Activity:

Antioxidant activity for leaf extract can be determined by using spectrophotometric methods.

Following spectrophotometric methods some techniques are given below:

➤ 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl assay or DPPH Assay

➤ 2,2-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid or ABTS assay

Extinguishing of colored-stable radical like DPPH and ABTS TFC TPC Metal Chelating activity is the foundation of these approaches. The biological system ability to scavenge plant metabolites is what cause this quenching.

1. DPPH Assay: The following the procedure have used to make the DPPH solution.

Preparation of DPPH Solution:

First, we took 250 ml of volumetric flask and cleaned it properly for the preparation of 1mM DPPH solution, then add 100ml of methanol in that flask, by using weighing balance weigh 0.0039gm of DPPH and add in the volumetric flask and shakes the solution until the compound has been completely dissolved and covered the flask with aluminum foil to stop the evaporation of methanol.

Procedure: The absorption of controlled solution was changed to 0.966 at 515max. In the process we use six test tubes and each of six test tubes was filled with 2.5ml of the essay solution and labelled with the sample composition that is to be added in it. Each of the sample solution was introduced 100µl to the test tube. The data were recorded at the interval of 5 mints, for thirty mints absorbance

was measured and data were recorded. The formula that is given is used to compute the percentage of the residual DPPH radical.

$$\text{DpphH\% Scavenging} = (1 - \text{Af}/\text{Ao}) \times 100$$

Af = Absorption of sample A = Absorbance of blank DPPH

After measuring the DPPH %age, graph was plotted.

2. ABTS Assay: For the preparation of ABTS solution two solution are mixed together. One solution is named as solution 1 and other is solution, by the addition of 0.0384gm of ABTS in 7.5ml of distilled water are dissolved in a capped test tube for the preparation of solutions 1. These two solutions were shake properly to take miscible solution. On the other hand, by mixing 0.0270gm of potassium per sulphate in 10ml of distilled water in 50ml of beaker to prepare solution no 2. To prepared ABTS solution, add 2.5 ml of solution 2in the solution 2 by shaking both the solution sudden color change of solution 1 occur after shaking, then prepared ABTS are placed in the refrigerator for 24 hours to covered it with aluminum foil.

PBS buffer preparation

Took 8.7gm NaCl and 1.8gm of $\text{k}_2\text{H}_2\text{Po}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are weighed and poured in 500ml beaker also with 200ml of distilled water stirrer the solution continuously until both the solutions are completely dissolved also add salt and after that Ph of solution were noted. One the other hand other solution was also prepared by dissolving KH_2PO_4 in a small amount of distilled water this solution was mainly used to adjusting the PH above solution and then the amount of solution raised to 1000ml.

Procedure:

At 734 max the absorption of stock solution of ABTS have to be adjusted to 0.716 by the addition of ABTS assay or any PBS buffer solution accordingly. And six test tubes have to be taken and, in each test, tube contain 2.9 ml of this solution, in each test tube add 10 of each sample composition by using micropipette and mixed the solution by proper shaking. And absorbance of each sample composition has to be noted after 8 mints, and also antioxidant potential of these sample measured with respect to percentage inhibition at 734nm here is mention below.

Inhibition (%) = $(A_f/A_o) \times 100$

Here, A_o = Absorbance of Blank ABTS Assay

A_f = Absorbance of sampled ABTS assay

After calculating the inhibition percentage, TEAC value for each percentage was calculated and also graph have to plotted between sample composition and TEAC.

3: Total Phenolic Content (TPC)➤ **Step:1**➤ **For Making 20% Sodium Carbonate**

Take 20g of sodium carbonate. Add 80ml of water, now boil the solution. After boiling it, cool it at room temperature. Small crystals will form when solution is cooled. Take few crystals and stay it over a night. After this filters it and make a volume of 100ml.

➤ **Step:2**

Take 40 micro liter sample with the help of pipette, add 3.16ml water. Now add F.C reagent. After this, mix gently solution for about 2 min. Stop shaking, keep it at rest for 8min. After

passing this time, add 600microlitre Na_2CO_3 , Put this solution in incubator for 30min at 40Celcius temperature. Note the Absorbance at 765nm.

4.Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)**Material Required:**➤ **NaOH (1M)**

Take 4g of sodium hydroxide add in 100ml water. 1M NaOH is prepared.

➤ **NaNO_2 (5%)**

Take 5g of NaNO_2 in 100ml of dd water. 5% of NaNO_2 is prepared.

➤ **AlCl_3 (10%)**

Add 5g of AlCl_3 in 50ml of dd water.

Method: Take 250 microliter extract of plant, add 1250 microliter of dis. Water in it. Now add 75 microliters of 5% NaNO_2 . Gently shake this for 2 min. After shaking, stay for 5 min. After 5min add 150 microliters of AlCl_3 and wait for 6 minutes. Add 500 microliter of NaOH solution and 275 microliters in it. Note absorbance at 510nm.

5.Metal Chelating Activity:**Protocol:**

1. Add 0.121g of ferrozine in 50ml flask and then add water 12mM in it.

2. Took 0.055g of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ IN 100 ml flask then add 2mM water in it.

Make the solution mixture of 10 μl sample ,50 μl ,200 μl of ferrozine to make total volume up to 4ml and also add methanol in this mixture. shacked the solution vigorously and stand 10 mints at the room temperature. The absorbance is to be noted at 562nm.Also run a blank solution without sample solution also add 100 μl of ethanol in place of sample.

$M. C.A = (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) \times 100 / A_{\text{control}}$

Antibacterial activity of platanus orientalis L. extract:

The procedure described was somewhat modified for this exercise, which include the following steps below here.

Sample solution and medium preparation: By using the same procedure as mentioned previously for antioxidant activity, the sample solution was made in various solvent composition. By using weighing balance weight 2.5 gram of nutrient broth and then added to the volumetric flask of 500ml also with 150ml of distilled water for the medium preparation. In the presence of magnetic stirrer whole the mixture has to be heated. Then slowly add 3gm of agar in the same heating mixture along with the continuous stirring and heating the mixture until the homogenous solution was prepared. And this solution then put through a 15 minute in autoclave at 1200c, three sterile petri dishes were utilized for each bacteria totaling six sterilized dishes each of the dish divided into three pieces. In the end of the process the autoclaved medium was poured into the three sectioned sterilized petri dishes and contain laminar flow and placed for the cooling. Each of the two sets of three petri dishes, each with three portions was labeled with the name of the organism it contained. Set No 1 for E. coli and Set No 2 for bacillus subtilis.

In Set No 1: After the agar medium had solidified in set no1, the glass spreader was used to evenly

disperse the E. coli culture on that surface. Following that, wells was created in each portion of each petri dish, the control was added to one section of each petri dish were inoculated with sample solutions. penicillin was used as a control. Each dish comprised a section of control and two sections of sample composition. One section for each sample composition. Six sample mixture were therefore put into three petri plates. At the ends all the dishes were caped with the sterilized lid also tape wrapped on each dish;24 hours were spent incubator set at 37 and finding were documented at the end of the period. For set two, the same procedure was followed without the bacteria. Bacillus subtilis was added to this collection.

Antidiabetic Activity (In Vitro).

The alpha Glucosidase inhibition assay:

To assess their potential as anti-diabetic agents, plant extracts were tested for their ability to block a-glucosidase. In 70μ of (50Mm) phosphate buffer with a pH of 6.8 and 1 unit/ml of yeast-glucosidase, extracts (10-100g) were suspended. Then after performing a 10-minute incubation at 37 degrees Celsius with the prepared mixture, the reaction was started by adding 10 ml of substrate nitrophenol glucopyranoside (5mM). the 405nm absorbance was noted for p nitrophenol released after 30 mint incubation as result of reaction.

Fig: Spectro UV-Visible Double Beam

The following mathematical connection was utilized to calculate the % inhibition after triplicate measurement were taken.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = (A_b - A_s / A_b) \times 100$$

AB=Absorbance of blank (without extract), As =Absorbance of sample (with extracts)

The reference standard is used Acarbose and results were represented as IC 50 value (μg/ml) for each extract.

Results:

Platanus leaves was lyophilized and ultrasonically processed to obtain the leaf extracts. Various solvent composition was made by mixing ethanol and distilled water in various ratios. Because it works well as an extraction solvent in nutraceuticals, in which ethanol was chosen as the solvent. The extraction of metabolites from the leaves was done using this solvent. For the incasement of effectiveness of extraction composition made up of organic solvent and aqueous medium to freeze dried leaves of understudy plant. Composition no 6 which contain no alcohol, displayed the highest extraction percentage. According to report composition No 5 the highest extracted yield for platanus orientalis leaves at 6.28%, when compared to composition using different solvents. However, a 0% of ethanol mixed had to the lowest yield. In cases involving platanus, it was shown that mixing ethanol did not effectively extract the maximum yield. So, the aqueous medium was the most efficient solvent with content of ethanol for the extraction of maximum yield. We can estimate for the procedure that if we increase the content of ethyl alcohol the extracted %yield got increases

in the solvent composition. In the case composition No 1,2,3 and 5 it was to be noted that there is not much change in extract yield, and ethanolic contents is 100,80,40, and 60 respectively. In the composition no 5 the sudden change in extract yield was occurred and 0% of ethanolic contents. The most significant attribute, the solvent properly, was most likely to blame for the variation in yield extract acquired from solvent composition. Additionally, it is important to consider the polarity of the plant metabolites that will the extracted. Methanol when used as solvent, it is shown in table that 100% contained sample show more yield which is about 5.29% and the lowest yield is at zero which is 2.945%.

Although it is not necessary for high yield to demonstrate effective biological activities, as indicated by study, the maximum yield in instance of pure media showed that it contained the majorities of soluble metabolites. So, the potential of biological activities depends on amount of bioactive compound in that yield. Hence proved that ethanol and methanol is the greatest solvent for generating the highest extraction yield percentage for platanus orientalis, according to recent research.

Fig:Graphical Representation of extract yield in solvents composition

GC-MS Analysis: Antioxidant activity:

Antioxidant activity includes different assay that have been explained. These are DPPH, ABTS, CFT, TPC and Metal chelating. For the assessment of antioxidant activity, following techniques are trustworthy, sensitive, quick and very simple to apply. These methods are used for the measurements of *Platanus orientalis* L. in different solvents.

2,2 diphenyl -1-picrylhydrazyl Test (DPPH):

First test that have done is dpph test. It is simply requiring a visible spectrometer which to determine the plant metabolites. It is mostly used for evaluating radical protection from plant metabolites. Composition was prepared in which dpph solution was added. Before adding the dpph, composition was in dark color but after adding the dpph, they turned into colorless. Quantitative representation of dpph test for *Platanus orientalis* L. is given below.

Fig: Graphical representation of Dpph %.

From above methanol graph it is clear that 40% composition have highest dpph potential among all other compositions. So, platanus orientalis show more antioxidant activity while its extract mix with methanol solvent. Lowest activity shown at 0% methanol composition. From above ethanol graph it is clear that 40% composition have highest dpph potential among all other compositions. So, platanus orientalis show more antioxidant activity while its extract mix with

Ethanol solvent. Lowest activity shown at 20% Ethanol composition.

ABTS test: ABTS (2,2-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid)). Trolox (6 hydroxy 2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman 2-carboxylic acid) used as standard.

Results of ABTS while using two types of solvents i.e ethanol and methanol are given below.

Table: TAEC values of methanol-based compositions.

Methanol	T ₁	T ₂	Absorbance	% absorbance	TAEC values
0%	4:23	4:31	0.238	66.94	6.75
20%	4:24	4:32	0.45	37.5	3.749
40%	4:25	4:33	0.044	93.88	9.496
60%	4:26	4:34	0.180	75	7.57
80%	4:27	4:35	0.45	37.5	3.749
100%	4:36	4:36	0.047	93.47	9.45

Ethanol	T ₁	T ₂	Absorbance	% absorbance	TAEC values
0%	4:16	4:24	0.283	60.69	6.11
20%	4:17	4:25	0.218	69.72	7.034
40%	4:18	4:26	0.060	91.66	9.27
60%	4:20	4:27	0.052	92.77	9.383
80%	4:21	4:28	0.109	84.86	8.577
100%	4:22	4:29	0.314	56.38	5.674

TFC:

Total flavonoid content test had done with types of solvents ethanol and methanol.

Methanol	Absorbance	%Absorbance	Value
0%	0.134	81.38	74068.9
20%	0.127	82.36	74959.8
40%	0.150	79.16	72050.7
60%	0.120	83.33	75841.6
80%	0.165	77.08	70159.8
100%	0.168	76.16	69323

Ethanol	Absorbance	%Absorbance	value
0%	0.125	82.63	75205
20%	0.130	81.94	74578
40%	0.229	68	61905
60%	0.231	67.9	61814
80%	0.149	79.3	72178
100%	0.186	74	67359.8

In above table it is clear that high absorbance percentage of 0% ethanol-based composition show it means water is also a best solvent. Plant also show high TFC value in presence of a polar solvent. Water is a good solvent. Lowest absorbance value showed by 40% composition but in other antioxidant test 40% composition show more results, it shows high absorbance also show

high antioxidant activity but, in this test, it shows less activity.

TPC: Total phenolic content test had done with ethanol and methanol.

When sodium carbonate adds its color change. Put in incubator for 30 min at 40 Celsius.

Methanol

Methanol	Absorbance	%Absorbance	Value
0%	0.183	0.7458	1683.75
20%	0.302	0.581	1271.75
40%	0.346	0.5194	1117.75
60%	0.230	0.681	1521.75
80%	0.384	0.4667	9806
100%	0.465	0.3542	704.75

Ethanol

Ethanol	Absorbance	%absorbance	Value
0%	0.143	0.8014	1822.75
20%	0.555	0.2292	393.25
40%	0.296	0.5889	1291.5
60%	0.392	0.4556	958.25
80%	0.238	0.6694	1492.75
100%	0.528	0.2667	486

In this antioxidant activity 0% in both methanol and ethanol show high absorbance value it means that without these organic solvent plant extract also shows high antioxidant activity. This activity is due to water presence; water is a polar solvent.

Lowest values in both tables 20% in ethanol and 100% almost in both solvents. It shows presence of this solvent can also affect the working of plant; it can affect the defense activity against pathogens or many other diseases.

Metal Chelating activity:

Graphical representation of metal chelating activity.

In metal chelating also methanol show high absorbance value in 0% composition but lowest value absorbance showed by 80% composition. I mean that organic solvents that used in this activity did not much effect on the activity of plant neither enhance nor it decrease it.

Antibacterial Activity:

Six different solution was prepared that have same extract amount but different compositions. Inhibition zone diameter is measured by this study, only one composition shows the result of antibacterial activity, it means that platanus orientalis L. plant extract has less antibacterial effect.

Antidiabetic Activity:

Results:

Table shows the Inhibition rate.

Sr. No.	Sample compositions	Sample absorbance (A _s) for α-Glucosidase	%inhibition for α-Glucosidase
1	Pure ethanol (100%)	0.93	28.96428
2	80% ethanol	0.911	30.66071
3	60% ethanol	0.985	24.05357
4	40% ethanol	0.783	42.08928
5	20% ethanol	1.01	21.82142
6	Pure methanol (100%)	0.81	39.67857
7	80% methanol	0.7	49.5
8	60% methanol	0.922	29.67857
9	40% methanol	0.656	53.42857
10	20% methanol	0.922	29.67857
11	Aqueous (0% ethanol or methanol)	0.98	24.5
12	Acarbose	0.18	95.92857

In Above table values of inhibition rate are given. Both solvent compositions I.e. methanol and

ethanol are given but highest inhibition rate is 95 of Acarbose.

Graphical Representation of Methanol and Ethanol % Inhibition in Vitro Activity

Conclusion:

The aim of this research is to find the chemical characteristics of *Platanus orientalis* L. different biological activities had performed to find its capability against any disease or any harm. Plant resists any harm or damage. It has

ability to protect itself. GC MS and HPLC help to find its component who are the basic fighter behind it. All research is very beneficial. Antioxidant activities are very helpful to understand the nature of plant. This plant shows a large variety of metabolites which help plant to protect itself. In pharmaceutical industries it is used as anti-inflammatory, pain reliever etc. It has a large aesthetic value in different countries.

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